

PHARMACEUTICALS

SEDATIVE ACTIVITY OF PURIFIED AQUEOUS EXTRACT OF HYPERICUM SCABRUM

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Abstract

*In the present study, a technology for obtaining a dry extract from the aerial parts of *Hypericum scabrum* was developed and optimized with consideration for the removal of accompanying hydrophilic impurities that hinder drying and reduce the concentration of active compounds. Purification of the concentrated aqueous extract was carried out by precipitating carbohydrates, polysaccharides, and pectin substances using 96% ethanol at a volume ratio of extract to ethanol of 1:4. Optimal spray drying parameters were established as follows: heat carrier inlet temperature of 150–160 °C, outlet temperature of 60–70 °C, solution concentration of 10–15%, feed rate of 3 L/h, and spray pressure of 0.15 MPa. The resulting dry extract exhibited stable physicochemical characteristics, including a yield of 6.0–6.4% and rutin content of 1.81–1.94%. Pharmacological studies on laboratory animals demonstrated that the dry extract possesses a pronounced sedative effect, particularly at a dose of 50 mg/kg. The developed technology can be applied for the industrial production of standardized phytopharmaceuticals based on *H. scabrum*.*

Keywords: *Hypericum scabrum, dry extract, flavonoids, rutin, extract purification, spray drying, sedative effect.*

Introduction

In medical practice, preparations based on St. John's wort (*Hypericum perforatum*) are primarily used as antidepressant agents. A universal technology for obtaining the substance "St. John's Wort Dry Extract" from the aerial parts of two species — *H. scabrum* and *H. perforatum* — was previously developed. This technology enables the production of a final product that meets the requirements of international regulatory and technical standards, aligned with those of the British Pharmacopoeia, with a hypericin content ranging from 0.25% to 0.3% [1–2].

To date, *Hypericum perforatum* has not been introduced into agricultural cultivation, and its natural habitats continue to diminish. This underscores the relevance of identifying alternative sources of raw plant material with comparable chemical composition and pharmacological activity. Although the genus *Hypericum* comprises 484 species, *H. perforatum* remains the most widely used in medical practice [3]. However, *H. scabrum* warrants attention, as its distribution range in Uzbekistan is significantly broader than that of *H. perforatum* [1].

Hypericum scabrum L. (family Hypericaceae) is a species native to the regions of Central and Western Asia. This plant is known for its high content of biologically active compounds, which contribute to its significant therapeutic potential. Its phytochemical composition includes flavonoids (such as rutin and quercetin), ascorbic and nicotinic acids, saponins, sugars, carotene, tocopherol, hypericin, choline, hyperoside, phytoncides, essential oils, as well as tannins, resinous substances, and bitter compounds. The wide range of these bioactive constituents provides the basis for the extensive use of *H. scabrum* in the treatment of various diseases. Traditionally, the plant has been employed in the management of inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity, disorders of the biliary and gastrointestinal tracts, and has also demonstrated efficacy in treating depressive conditions, insomnia, and elevated anxiety levels [4].

The aim of the present study is to develop a technology for obtaining a dry extract based on aqueous extraction from *Hypericum scabrum* and to investigate the sedative activity of the resulting preparation.

Materials and Methods

For the experiments, plant material from the aerial parts of *Hypericum scabrum* was collected between June 10 and June 15, 2024, in the vicinity of the village of Sidjak, located in the Bostanlyk district of the Tashkent region.

It has been established that rutin increases the levels of monoamines in the synaptic cleft by inhibiting monoamine oxidase — an enzyme responsible for the breakdown of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and noradrenaline [5].

Currently, new approaches to the standardization of St. John's wort raw material have been proposed, based on the determination of the content of two groups of biologically active substances: flavonoids and anthracene derivatives. The method involves simultaneous quantitative determination of the total flavonoids

expressed as rutin and the total anthracene derivatives expressed as hypericin [6, 7].

Considering the above, during the development of the technology for obtaining a dry extract based on aqueous extraction from the aerial parts of *Hypericum scabrum*, the total flavonoid content expressed as rutin was selected as the target active compound.

The quantitative determination of total flavonoids in the obtained samples was performed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

To determine the rutin content, a test solution of the sample was prepared as follows: approximately 10 mg (exact amount recorded) of the sample was placed into a 100 ml volumetric flask, then 30 ml of 40% ethanol solution was added. The volume was then brought up to the mark with 40% ethanol solution to prepare a solution with a concentration of 0.1 mg/ml.

Similarly, a standard rutin solution was prepared. Approximately 10 mg of the rutin standard was placed into a 100 ml volumetric flask, 40 ml of 40% ethanol solution was added, and the volume was brought to the mark with 40% ethanol solution and mixed. This resulted in a solution with a concentration of approximately 0.1 mg/ml. Then, 1 ml of this solution was taken, transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, and diluted to the mark with the appropriate solution.

To verify the chromatograph's performance, the standard solution was injected five times. Chromatograms showed identified peaks corresponding to the standard solutions, and their areas were determined. The retention time was approximately 15.435 minutes.

The percentage content (X) of rutin in the investigated dry extract samples was calculated using the following formula:

$$X = \frac{S \cdot m_0 \cdot V \cdot P \cdot 100}{S_0 \cdot m \cdot V_0 \cdot (100 - W)};$$

where:

- S — peak area of rutin in the test sample solution;
- S_0 — peak area of rutin in the standard solution;
- m_0 — mass of the standard sample, in grams;
- m — mass of the test sample, in grams;
- P — purity of the standard sample, in percent;
- W — moisture content, in percent.

To study the removal of hydrophobic impurities, aqueous extracts from the aerial parts of *Hypericum scabrum* were obtained under dynamic conditions using the extraction method with circulation of the extractant [8, 9]. Twenty kilograms of crushed plant material were loaded into a jacketed extractor equipped with a circulation pump, and water was added at a raw material-to-extractant ratio of 1:6. Steam was supplied to the extractor jacket, and the extractant circulated from bottom to top at a temperature of 75 °C. The first extraction lasted 5 hours, after which the extract was drained. The procedure was repeated twice with fresh portions of purified water under similar conditions. The total liquid-to-solid ratio (hydromodule) was 1:18. The combined extracts were cooled and filtered through a Nutsche filter under vacuum (–0.8 to –0.4 kgf/cm²) us-

ing belting filter cloth. The resulting filtrate was concentrated under vacuum (-0.8 to -0.6 kgf/cm²) at 60 °C to a residual volume of 8% of the original.

The resulting concentrate was divided into four portions. To each portion, 96% ethanol was added in various volume ratios of concentrate to alcohol with vigorous stirring. The mixtures were kept in sealed containers for a specified time, after which the precipitate formed was separated by filtration. The obtained filtrates were further concentrated and dried at a temperature not exceeding 60 °C.

To optimize drying parameters of the purified aqueous flavonoid extract ensuring the required quality of the dry extract, experimental studies were conducted to determine the following parameters: inlet and outlet temperatures of the heat carrier, feed rate of the solution, and solution concentration.

These studies were performed using a spray dryer "Anhydro No. 2" (Denmark), with a drying chamber volume of 0.9 m³, heater power of 9 kW, and moisture evaporation capacity of up to 10 liters per hour when drying pure water [10, 11].

Spray Drying Experimental Conditions. For the experiments, aqueous extracts from 20 kg of *Hypericum scabrum* plant material were prepared according to the previously described procedure. After filtration, the extract was concentrated to 60% dry matter content. To the concentrate, 96% ethanol was added in a volume ratio of 1:4 under vigorous stirring. The mixture was kept in a sealed container for 6 hours, after which the precipitate was separated by filtration. The resulting filtrate was evaporated to completely remove the ethanol and then diluted with purified water to a dry matter content of 15%.

The prepared solution was divided into 20 equal portions, which were subjected to drying under varying conditions in a spray dryer. The experimental conditions were as follows:

- **Determination of optimal inlet temperature of the heat carrier:** The first five portions were dried at varying inlet temperatures while maintaining a constant outlet temperature of 70 °C, a feed rate of 4 L/h, and a spray pressure of 0.1 MPa.

- **Determination of optimal outlet temperature of the heat carrier:** The next five portions were dried at a fixed inlet temperature (155 ± 5 °C) and varying outlet temperatures, with a feed rate of 4 L/h and a spray pressure of 0.1 MPa.

- **Determination of optimal feed rate:** Portions 11–13 were dried at an inlet temperature of 155 ± 5 °C, outlet temperature of 65 ± 5 °C, various feed rates, and a constant spray pressure of 0.1 MPa.

- **Determination of optimal solution concentration:** Portions 14–17 were prepared with dry matter concentrations of 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%. Drying was performed at an inlet temperature of 155 ± 5 °C, outlet temperature of 65 ± 5 °C, feed rate of 3 L/h, and spray pressure of 0.1 MPa.

- **Determination of optimal spray pressure:**

The last three portions (18–20) were dried at an inlet temperature of 155 ± 5 °C and outlet temperature of 65 ± 5 °C, at different spray pressures of 0.1 , 0.15 , and 0.2 MPa, with corresponding feed rates.

The sedative activity of the dry St. John's wort extract (SEM), obtained using the proposed technology, was evaluated in mice according to the method described in [12].

The dry St. John's wort extract (SEM) was administered orally once daily for 7 days at doses of 25 , 50 , and 100 mg/kg. Laboratory mice weighing 18 – 20 g were used in the experiment. Three experimental groups corresponding to the administered doses and one control group were formed, each consisting of six animals.

Locomotor activity was assessed by counting the number of crossings made by mice under a glass dome (diameter 25 cm) on a table surface within 1 minute. The crossings were counted before administration and 2 hours after dosing [12]. The mean locomotor activity was calculated for each group.

Results and Discussion

The aqueous extract from the aerial parts of *H. scabrum* contains, in addition to flavonoids, hydrophilic accompanying substances such as carbohydrates, polysaccharides, and pectin compounds. The presence of these components in the target product reduces the concentration of active substances—flavonoids. Moreover, preliminary experimental results showed that the presence of hydrophilic impurities in the aqueous flavonoid solution from *H. scabrum* complicates the drying process, reducing the efficiency of obtaining a high-quality dry extract.

Therefore, to purify the concentrated aqueous extract, a method of precipitating carbohydrates and other hydrophilic substances by adding ethanol was employed. One of the key factors influencing the efficiency of this process is the degree of concentration of the residue and its volumetric ratio to ethanol. As a precipitating agent, 96% ethanol was used, considering its low toxicity and widespread use in the pharmaceutical industry.

The results demonstrated that increasing the amount of ethanol enhances the rutin content in the final dry extract. However, this also led to darkening of the product color, which was attributed to the extraction of pigment compounds. When insufficient ethanol was added, the yield of dry extract increased, but the rutin content decreased due to ineffective precipitation of accompanying substances. Thus, the optimal protocol was chosen as follows: concentration of the aqueous extract from the aerial parts of *H. scabrum* to 8% of the initial volume, followed by precipitation of hydrophilic impurities by adding 96% ethanol in a volume ratio of residue to ethanol of 1:4 (Table 1).

Table 1

Effect of the Amount of Added 96% Ethanol on the Yield and Quality of the Dry Extract			
Concentrate-to-alcohol ratios	Dry extract yield % of raw material mass	Rutin content in dry extract, %	Dry extract color
1:2	6,8	1,2	Brown
1:3	6,6	1,4	Brown
1:4	6,5	1,8	Reddish brown
1:5	6,8	1,9	Dark brown

After precipitation of the accompanying substances, the sediment was separated, and the filtrate was dried. Spray drying was selected as the drying method. Therefore, the study proceeded with determining the optimal operating conditions for the spray dryer.

The conducted studies on determining the optimal inlet temperature of the heat carrier into the drying chamber showed that increasing the temperature enhances the productivity of the spray dryer. However, at temperatures above 180 °C, deterioration of the organ-

oleptic properties of the resulting dry extract was observed — a burnt odor appeared, along with worsening taste and darkening of the color.

Furthermore, at elevated temperatures, losses of the target product increased due to the formation of fine and light powder particles that were carried away with the heated air stream. When the temperature dropped below 150 °C, adhesion of extract particles to the internal walls of the drying chamber was noted, which also negatively affected the yield and quality of the product.

Based on these results, the optimal inlet temperature was chosen in the range of 150–160 °C (Table2).

Table 2

Effect of Heat Carrier Inlet Temperature on the Drying Process

Inlet temperature of the heat carrier, °C	Dry extract yield % of raw material mass	Water content in dry extract (%)	Dry extract color
140	5,2	3,1	Brown
150	6,2	3,2	Reddish brown
160	6,0	3,0	Reddish brown
170	5,2	2,8	Brown
180	4,8	2,4	Dark brown

The experimental results for determining the heat carrier outlet temperature revealed that at an outlet temperature of 50 °C, the moisture content in the dry extract was high, while at 90 °C, the loss of dry extract increased. This can be explained by the fact that as

moisture decreases, the product density lowers, causing a greater amount of the product to be carried away with the air stream. Therefore, the heat carrier outlet temperature was selected to be in the range of 60–70 °C (Table 3).

Table 3

Effect of Heat Carrier Outlet Temperature on the Drying Process

Heat carrier outlet temperature (°C)	Dry extract yield % of raw material mass	Water content in dry extract (%)	Dry extract color
50	5,4	6,2	Brown
60	6,3	3,9	Reddish brown
70	6,1	3,7	Reddish brown
80	5,5	2,2	Light brown
90	5,1	1,5	Dark brown

The study continued to determine the optimal feed rate of the solution to the spray dryer. According to the experimental data (Table 4), it was established that the best balance between product yield, quality characteristics of the dry extract, and process stability is achieved at a solution feed rate of 3 L/h.

In terms of the drying chamber volume, this corresponds to a productivity of 3.5 L/h·m³. This regime ensured uniform atomization, minimal losses, and high quality of the final product.

Table 4

Effect of Solution Feed Rate on the Drying Process

Solution feed rate (L/h)	Dry extract yield % of raw material mass	Mass fraction of moisture in dry extract, %
2	5,7	3,0
3	6,2	3,2
4	6,0	3,8

The conducted studies on determining the optimal concentration of the solution showed that the most suitable concentration for spray drying was 10–15% dry matter. Solutions with a lower concentration (5%) contained an excessive amount of moisture, which led to

reduced drying efficiency and increased energy consumption. At the same time, when the dry matter concentration reached 20%, significant darkening of the resulting powder was observed (Table 5).

Table 5

Effect of Solution Concentration on the Drying Process

Dry matter content in the feed solution (%)	Dry extract yield % of raw material mass	Water content in dry extract (%)	Dry extract color
5	5,4	6,1	Brown
10	6,1	2,7	Light brown
15	6,3	3,0	Reddish brown
20	5,5	1,8	Dark brown

The degree of atomization of the solution in the drying chamber directly depends on the air pressure supplied to the nozzle. Optimal pressure promotes the formation of fine droplets, uniform distribution of the solution within the drying chamber, and, consequently, efficient drying.

During the experiments, three spray pressure levels were tested: 0.1, 0.15, and 0.2 MPa. The results in-

dicated that a pressure of 0.15 MPa was optimal. It ensured stable nozzle operation, uniform drying without the formation of large undried droplets or dry residue on the chamber walls, and resulted in the highest quality dry extract.

Based on the results obtained, a technology for producing dry extract from *Hypericum scabrum* was developed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Block diagram of the production process for dry extract from the aerial parts of *H. Scabrum*

The proposed technology was tested in the production of five batches of dry extract from the aerial parts of *H. scabrum*. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 6.

Table 6

Analysis Results of Five Batches of Dry Extract from the Aerial Parts of *H. scabrum*

№ Lot number	Dry extract yield % of raw material mass	Rutin content in dry extract, %	Mass fraction of moisture in dry extract, %
2	6,4	1,81	3,8
2	6,2	1,94	2,9
3	6,3	1,86	3,4
4	6,0	1,83	3,6
5	6,2	1,90	3,1

As shown in Table 6, the yield and quality parameters (moisture content and rutin content) of all five batches of dry extract remain stable. This confirms the reproducibility of the proposed technology and its suitability for use under production conditions.

The study of the effects of *Hypericum* dry extract (HDE) on the locomotor activity of mice demonstrated

that all tested doses exhibited a calming effect. The most pronounced effect was observed with the administration of HDE at a dose of 50 mg/kg for 7 days, resulting in a 38.2% reduction in locomotor activity. In contrast, the 25 mg/kg and 100 mg/kg doses produced inconsistent effects (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Effect of *Hypericum* dry extract on the locomotor activity of mice

Note. * — statistically significant compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$).

The study on the effect of *Hypericum* dry extract (HDE) on the duration of sleep induced by sodium ethaminal showed that in the control group of mice, the average sleep duration was 48.2 ± 1.6 minutes. Admin-

istration of HDE at doses of 25, 50, and 100 mg/kg resulted in increases in sleep duration by 29.7%, 56.2%, and 37.1%, respectively. As shown in Table 7, the most pronounced sedative effect was observed at the 50 mg/kg dose.

Table 7.

Effect of *Hypericum* dry extract (HDE) on the duration of sodium ethaminal-induced sleep in mice (Mean \pm SEM, n=6)

Experimental conditions	Doses, mg/kg	Duration of lateral position (sleep) in minutes
Control (sodium thiopental)	40	48,2 \pm 1,6
SEC	25	62,5 \pm 1,9
	50	75,3 \pm 2,1
	100	66,1 \pm 2,0

Note. * — statistically significant compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions

1. It was found that the aqueous extract from the aerial parts of *Hypericum scabrum* contains a significant amount of accompanying hydrophilic substances (carbohydrates, polysaccharides, and pectins), which reduce the concentration of target flavonoids and complicate the drying process.

2. An effective purification method for the concentrated aqueous extract was developed, based on the precipitation of hydrophilic impurities using 96% ethanol at a volume ratio of extract to ethanol of 1:4. This approach enables the removal of unwanted components and increases the rutin content in the final product.

3. Optimal spray drying parameters were established to ensure stable quality characteristics of the dry extract: inlet air temperature of 150–160 °C; outlet air temperature of 60–70 °C; feed rate of 3 L/h (equivalent to 3.5 L/h·m³); feed solution concentration before drying of 10–15%; and atomizing air pressure of 0.15 MPa.

4. The developed technology for producing dry extract from the aerial parts of *H. scabrum* was tested over five production batches, confirming the stability of product yield (6.0–6.4%), rutin content (1.81–1.94%), and moisture content (2.9–3.8%). These results demonstrate the reproducibility and technological reliability of the process.

5. Pharmacological studies showed that the dry extract of *H. scabrum* exhibited sedative effects at all tested doses. The most pronounced sedative effect was observed at a dose of 50 mg/kg, which caused the greatest reduction in mice locomotor activity (by 38.2% compared to control) and the highest increase in sleep duration (by 56.2%).

6. The obtained data support the recommendation of the dry extract of *Hypericum scabrum*, produced by the proposed technology, as a promising plant-based sedative agent.

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